

The Influence of a Service Instrument for Measuring Patient Satisfaction in Multispecialty Teaching Hospital at Odisha

Pritipadma Mohanty¹; Dr. Aurolipy ^{*.1,2}

¹Research Scholar, Institute of Business and Computer studies, Hospital administration, Siksha 'O' Anusandhan Deemed to be University, K8, Kalinga Nagar, Bhubaneswar-751003, Odisha, INDIA

¹Associate Professor, Institute of Business and Computer studies, Hospital administration, Siksha 'O' Anusandhan Deemed to be University, K8, Kalinga Nagar, Bhubaneswar-751003, and Odisha, INDIA

² Head of The Department, Quality, IMS and SUM Hospital, Siksha 'O' Anusandhan Deemed to be University, K8, Kalinga Nagar, Bhubaneswar-751003, and Odisha, INDIA

Corresponding Author:- Dr. Aurolipy ^{*.1,2}

Abstract:-

➤ Introduction:

Patient satisfaction plays an important role to measure the service quality. Many factors directly or indirectly contribute towards the satisfaction of patients, but looking into the current scenario healthcare sector gives more priority to patient satisfaction which indirectly act as word of mouth. Presently the patient's expectation level has much increased to reach at that point healthcare sector gives priority to word of mouth than observation. Some common factors which contribute towards the satisfaction of patient are commonly used to measure the quality of healthcare.

➤ The Objectives of the study:

(a)To study the satisfaction level of inpatient at a multispecialty teaching hospital.(b)To study the different contributory factors affecting patient satisfaction. (c)To analyze the various gaps to improve patient satisfaction.

➤ Materials and Methods:

The descriptive study was done in multispecialty teaching hospital. About 3000 inpatient feedback forms were analyzed for the study. All the data were entered in Microsoft excel sheet and analyzed using SPSS software package.

➤ Result:

It was found that, the patients were satisfied by the services provided by the hospital i.e., in Front office (TAT Admission Process94%, Timely Discharge process91%, Courteous of staff93%, Information about each cost of treatment and services89%, Information on hospital regulations85%) , in Doctor care (Service of attending doctors 96%, Counselling of patient / patient attendant by doctor 96%) , in Dietary services (Quality of food service78%, Food timely served 82%, Counselling by Dietician 91%, Courteous of staff 97%) , in Nursing services (Attitude and behaviour of nurses 89%, Timely response to needs 92%, Description of the

progression and course of treatment 92%, Medication Administration 91%) , in Pharmacy services (Timely Dispensing 79%, Availability of all medicines 90%), in Housekeeping services 76%, in Radiology services 69%, in Lab services 65% and 85% of the patients satisfied with the other services .

➤ Conclusion:

To conclude, after availing the healthcare service the patient shows its satisfaction and dissatisfaction in various areas. Thus, all deficiencies shall be addressed by the hospital with immediate effect to convert the dissatisfaction to satisfaction of inpatient in multispecialty teaching hospital, Odisha.

Keywords:- Patient Satisfaction, Patient Expectation, Multispecialty Teaching Hospital, Improvement Service Quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

Customer / patient expectation are the opinion about services provided by hospital is used as a yardstick against which the performance of the service is judged. The desired service is that which a patient expects from the hospital. Adequate service means when a patient fails to achieve the desired service[1].

It is a measure of service quality by the patient as they want to meet their expectations to be fulfilled. When the expectations are not fulfilled then dissatisfaction of patient arises. Patient satisfaction is a valid indicator used by the hospital to measure its service quality and also measure the areas where the service provided is not matching with patient expectation [2].

For hospital satisfied patients plays an important role of branding as indirectly they promote through word of mouth. The satisfied patients are more likely to use the medical services, keep good relation with healthcare providers and also directly or indirectly recommend the

hospital to other. As the patient's recommendation is from his/her own past or present experience, so it is mostly accepted by others than advertisement. Many studies accepted the higher patient satisfaction basis to many benefits to healthcare i.e., customer loyalty, improve branding and retention of patient, consistency in service and profitability [3].

Patient dissatisfaction parameter also provides an opportunity to the healthcare to identify different lacunas and find out the Root cause along with corrective and preventive action.

In the growing competitive healthcare sector, the service quality is important to provide service in the market. The management of service quality helps the management to judge each parameter of the service provided and also measure the outcome. By this it helps the management to maintain the consistency in service delivery, meeting the challenging, handling, demanding and changing expectations of the various types of patients. Thus, patient satisfaction survey is the tool used for weighing each parameter, knowing the expectation of the patient in addition to weighing the level of expectations meet and the level of dissatisfaction level of the patients, which provides an opportunity for self-assessment of healthcare and how to improve in the various areas where it is not meeting the expectation of the patients [4].

Patients are increasingly more demanding nowadays with higher level of expectation. It becomes very difficult to attract new patients. Thus, patient satisfaction tool can also be used for assessment of financial growth of the hospital. More satisfied patients generally attract more new patients by word of mouth, when indirectly they act as brand ambassador. Since it attracts more patients, so the healthcare can use patient satisfaction survey tool to achieve operational standard excellence in some major areas of specialty [5].

The impact of satisfaction also shows the quality process in healthcare. Thus, the continuity of quality process leads to the satisfaction of more and more patients. It helps to create quality culture in the hospital where every service will be systematic and automatic. This creates pious environment where the patient care is given more value and also the commitment and dedication of employees towards the patient care. This indirectly creates healthy and pious environment where patient feel more secured and also got an automatically healing effect so that before treatment patient feel secured and cured [6].

Thus, patients' opinion can be used as best source as they suggest valuable points related to patient care which might not be thought by management from patient perspective. So, patient opinion can be used for future planning & strategic transformation [7].

To survive in the competition the healthcare should also address the dissatisfaction level of patient. To get 100% satisfaction level is practically difficult unless until the dissatisfaction level of the patient is addressed. It has to practically evaluate the employees and find out the root cause analysis with implementation of corrective and preventive action.

➤ *Objective:*

- *To study the satisfaction level of inpatient at a multispecialty teaching hospital.*
- *To study the different contributory factors affecting patient satisfaction.*
- *To analyze the various gaps to improve patient satisfaction.*

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Study Design:*

The descriptive study was done in multispecialty teaching hospital.

➤ *Study Area:*

The research was carried out among the admitted patient of wards and cabins in a multispecialty teaching hospital.

➤ *Study Tool:*

The hospital in house patients (IPD) feedback form is used for the study. About 3000 IPD feedback forms were analyzed for the study. For the study, the April, May, and June 2023 feedback forms were used. All of the feedback form data was imported into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and evaluated with the SPSS software program. The analysis of patient satisfaction with the various hospital services employed descriptive statistics, such as frequency and percentages. Patient comments included ratings of excellent, good, average, poor. The patient gave each service a score, with excellent and good scores indicating satisfaction and average and poor scores indicating dissatisfaction. The following sections were included on the hospital's IPD feedback form:

- *Experience with Front office services.*
- *Experience with Doctors care services.*
- *Experience with Dietary services.*
- *Experience with nursing services.*
- *Experience with Housekeeping services.*
- *Experience with Radiology services.*
- *Experience with Lab services.*
- *Experience with Pharmacy services.*
- *Experience with Other services (i.e., cafeteria, security, lift, toilet, drinking water, seating area etc.) was taken as overall hospital ratings.*

Study period: 3 months (April, May, June).

III. RESULT

Table 1 Feedback from Inpatients on the Survey

Sl. No.	Division		Excellent	Good	Average	Poor
1	Front office	TAT Admission Process	33.33%	60.66%	5%	1%
		Timely Discharge process	31%	59.66%	7%	2.33%
		Courteous of staff	34%	59.33%	4.33%	2.33%
		Information about each cost of treatment and services	30.66%	58%	6.66%	4.66%
		Information on hospital regulations	30.66%	54.33%	8.33%	6.66%
2	Doctor care	Service of attending doctors	44%	52.33%	2.66%	1%
		Counselling of patient / patient attendant by doctor	45.33%	51%	2.33%	1.33%
3	Dietary services	Quality of food service	26%	52.33%	17.33%	4.33%
		Food timely served	28%	53.66%	15%	3.33%
		Counselling by Dietician	38.33%	52.33%	8%	1.33%
		Courteous of staff	41.33%	55.33%	2.33%	1%
4	Nursing services	Attitude and behaviour of nurses	42.33%	46.66%	7.66%	3.33%
		Timely response to needs	43.33%	49%	6.66%	1%
		Description of the progression and course of treatment	43%	48.66%	6.33%	2%
		Medication Administration	43.33%	48%	6.33%	2.33%
5	House keeping	The facility's cleanliness met your expectations	26%	49.66%	19%	5.33%
6.	Radiology services	Timely reporting	27%	42.33%	26.33%	4.33%
7.	Lab services	Timely reporting	26%	39%	28.66%	6.33%
8.	Pharmacy services	Timely Dispensing	36%	42.66%	18%	3.33%
		Availability of all medicines	42.66%	47%	8%	2.33%
9.	Others	Overall services this hospital provides	38.66%	46.66%	11.33%	3.33%

IV. DISCUSSION

➤ Front Office

The percentage of patients and attendees who said the TAT for admission was excellence, good, average, and poor was 33.33%, 60.66%, 5%, and 1%, for a total of 94% satisfied patients and 6% dissatisfied patients/attendees. In terms of the briefing on Information on hospital regulations, 30.66% of patients thought it was excellence and 58% thought it was good, suggesting that 89% of the patients were satisfied. With 6.66% rating it as average and 4.66%

rating it as poor, 11% of the patients were not happy. 93% of patients were satisfied with the front office staff's courtesy (including 34% and 59.33% of those who chose excellence and good), while 7% were dissatisfied (including 4.33% and 2.33% of those who chose average and poor) (Graph 1 and Table 1). Overall, 91% of patients were satisfied with the discharge process while 9% were not. So, a good percentage of patients were found to be satisfied with both the physical and behavioral dimensions of service and the overall patient satisfaction is good.

Graph 1 Patients’ Satisfaction in Front Office Services

➤ *Doctors Care*

Nearly 44% of patients/attendants thought the service provided by attending doctors during their interactions with them was excellent, 52.33% thought it was good, indicating 96% of satisfied patients, while 2.66% said it was average and only 1% said it was poor, indicating 4% of dissatisfied patients (Graph 2 and Table 1). Nearly 45.33% of patients/attendants believed the doctor's counselling was excellent, and 51% felt it was good, indicating 96% of the patients were satisfied. In contrast, 2.33% said it was average, and only 1.33% said it was poor, indicating 4% of the patients were unsatisfied.

Graph 2: Patients’ Satisfaction in Doctors Care

➤ *Dietary Services*

Approximately 26% of patients rated it as excellent, 52.33% as good, 17.33% as average, and 4.33% as poor (Graph 3 and Table 1). Overall, 78% of patients were pleased with the caliber of the hospital food offered, while 22% were not. Regarding the timely delivery of food, 82% of patients reported being satisfied (including 28% and 53.66% of those who chose excellent and good), whereas 18% of patients (including 15% and 3.33% of those who chose average and poor) reported being unsatisfied. These two aspects of the nutritional services are the biggest turnoffs.

Dietician counseling left patients 91% satisfied (including 38.33% and 52.33% of patients who chose excellent and good), whereas 9% were unsatisfied (with 8% and 1.33% of patients choosing average and poor). Regarding the staff's courtesy, 97% of patients expressed satisfaction (including 41.33% and 55.33% of patients who chose excellent and good), while 3% of patients who chose average and poor expressed dissatisfaction (including 2.33% and 1% of those patients).

Graph 3: Patients' Satisfaction in Dietary Services

➤ *Nursing Services*

Patients felt that 43% was excellent, 48.66% was good, 6.33% was average, and 2% was poor with regard to the nurses' attitude and behavior, timely response to needs, descriptions of the progression and course of treatment, and the administration of medication to patients (Graph 4 and Table 1). Overall, 91% of patients expressed satisfaction with the nursing services, compared to 9% who expressed displeasure.

Graph 4: Patients' Satisfaction in Nursing Services

➤ *Housekeeping*

Concerning satisfaction of respondents with the housekeeping services and cleanliness of the hospital environment, 26% and 49.66% chose excellent and good respectively while 19% and 5.33% said they were average and poor in that order (Graph 5 and Table 1). This indicates, 76% of patients were satisfied with the clean lines maintained while 24% were not.

Graph 5: Patients' Satisfaction in Housekeeping Services

➤ *Radiology Services*

Regarding timely reporting of radiology services, 27% felt it was excellent, 42.33% felt good, 26.33% felt it was average, 4.33% of them said it to be poor (Graph 6 and Table 1). Overall, 69% of patients were satisfied, while 31% were dissatisfied. It was one of the major dissatisfiers.

Graph 6: Patients' Satisfaction in Radiology Services

➤ *Lab Services*

Regarding timely reporting of lab services, 26% felt it was excellent, 39% felt good, 28.66% felt it was average, 6.33% of them said it to be poor (Graph 7 and Table 1). Overall, 65% of patients were satisfied, while 35% were dissatisfied. It was one of the major dissatisfiers.

Graph 7: Patients’ Satisfaction in Lab Services

➤ *Pharmacy Services*

Approximately 36% of patients rated it as excellent, 42.66% as good, 18% as average, and 3.33% as poor (Graph 8 and Table 1). In general, 79% of patients were satisfied with how quickly their medications were dispensed in the hospital, whereas 21% were not. One of the main sources of unhappiness was it. 90% of patients in the hospital were content with the availability of all medications, including 42.66% and 47% of those who chose excellent and good, respectively, while 10% including 8% and 2.33% of those who chose average and poor.

Graph 8: Patients’ Satisfaction in Pharmacy Services

➤ *Other Services*

Regarding overall services this hospital provides, 38.66% felt it was excellent, 46.66% felt good, 11.33% felt it was average, 3.33% of them said it to be poor (Graph 9 and Table 1). Overall, 85% of patients were satisfied, while 15% were dissatisfied.

Graph 9: Patients' Satisfaction in Other Services

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

We were reminded of some areas that require improvement in order to improve the hospital's service after conducting an assessment of patient satisfaction with inpatient care. Consequently, the following advice is given.

➤ *Front Office:*

Major tariff rate shall be displayed Infront of front office, lab and radiology so that the patient can aware about the cost to be in curved if they avail any service. During admission general consent shall be taken from all the patient explaining about the terms and conditions of admission process, cost, facility provided etc. Scope of service of each department shall be displayed in hospital along with the service not provided by hospital so that there wouldn't be any confusion among the patients. Information booklet shall be provided to the patient at the time of admission comprising of patient rights and responsibility, types of services available, accreditation status, rules and regulation of hospital.

➤ *Doctors Care:*

Majority of the patients are satisfied with the doctors and the same benchmark will be maintained.

➤ *Dietary Services:*

The patients are little dissatisfied about the quality and quantity of food. The breakfast shall be revised and the dietician should ensure the therapeutic diet should be tasty. Common idli and upma in breakfast for general patient should be modified. Dietician should atleast meet randomly the patients of cabins and ICU (stable patients) to assess the nutritional value and palate of food. There were some complaints of normal diet given to diabetic patient which needs strict monitoring by dietician and F&B manager.

➤ *Nursing Services:*

It was observed that patients are satisfied with the nursing services. But still continuous training is required to maintain the quality.

➤ *Housekeeping Services:*

The common toilets need more frequency of cleanliness although it was cleaned three times. The corridor, ward, lobby, waiting area shall be deep cleaned in the evening rather than in the day time. A team shall be constituted with HK executive and supervisors for this purpose. Housekeeping staff was not sufficient to manage the inpatient areas which requires to be addressed by the authority.

➤ *Radiology Services and Lab Services:*

Since the workload has increased, it is difficult to maintain the reporting time. Decentralization process to be initiated along with more data entry operators to streamline the reporting time. The patient shall get message in their mobile regarding the collection of reporting to avoid unnecessary chaos. The radiology and lab department shall display the TAT of reporting of each modality for the awareness of the patient. Patient shall not complain for the late reporting.

➤ *Pharmacy Services:*

To streamline the TAT of dispensing the hospital should have indenting through software than manual. The ward pharmacist shall be displayed floor wise in each shift to do the co-ordination between ward and pharmacy.

➤ *Other Services:*

The overall areas need to be improved to meet the satisfaction patient. Canteen services needs to be improved. The vulnerable patients should use lift than other. Security services needs to be more improvised, including CCTV surveillance of the entire hospital, security plan, single entry and exit point, visitors' management through visitor pass system.

VI. CONCLUSION

Feedback is the key parameter for assessment of service quality of hospital. Many factors directly and indirectly contribute for the patient satisfaction. Most of the patients were satisfied where their expectation satisfied i.e., doctors care and nursing service. The patient had the highest satisfaction level with doctor and nursing services. But still, it needs improvement. Most importantly the services which need to be addressed immediately i.e., Dietary service (Quality of food service, Food timely served), Housekeeping service, Radiology service, Lab service, Pharmacy service (Timely dispensing). The other services need improvement in some specific areas which requires to be addressed. The hospital is required to identify the root causes of the dissatisfaction parameter and practical analysis by manager to develop strategies. The managers should using the quality tool shall initiate the corrective and preventive action and check the continuity by assessing various indicator on regular basis. Thus, continuous improvement of service quality can be maintained by analyzing the indicator on regular basis.

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